

Agricultural Policy– What does Donald Rumsfeld have to do with it?

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Donald Rumsfeld famously once said: *“As we know, there are known knowns; there are things we know we know. We also know there are known unknowns; that is to say we know there are some things we do not know. But there are also unknown unknowns—the ones we don't know we don't know.”* He took stick for this, but for me his speech increasingly reminds us of where we are with agricultural policy at the movement.

The known-knowns (the direction of travel): It is becoming ever clearer that the future of agricultural support is not what it used to be. The Bute House agreement between the SNP and the Green Party commits to a new Bill being laid in the Scottish Parliament in 2023 that will set out new policies and support mechanisms to be launched in 2025. That Bill will supposedly be designed to *“ensure the sector makes the emission reductions required to contribute to Scotland's world-leading emissions targets, to support and deliver nature restoration and a just transition to net zero, and to produce high quality food.”* As the curtain came down on the Scottish Government's 100 day post-election commitment period the new Agriculture Reform Implementation Oversight Board (ARIOB) was announced and the *“Agricultural transition – first steps towards our national policy”* consultation was launched. These both provide some indication of where the Scottish Government's minds are on policy development. Firstly the ARIOB shows a commitment by officials to continue the Farmer Led Groups approach to co-construction of future agricultural policy provided all parties work together and agree to the policy objectives and delivery tools. The failure of the Farming and Food Production Future Policy Group to agree on key delivery principles remains a reminder that this collaborative approach is not be as easy as it first seems – but the prize means it is worth trying. Secondly, the Transition consultation, and the recent National Test Programme announcement from Mairi Gougeon, Cabinet Secretary for Rural Affairs, provides further confirmation of the direction of travel. Environmental baselining is emphasised – if you don't know where you are starting from, how do you start a journey or choose the path you are going to take. There is to be some additional support over the next few years to help this baselining process (carbon footprinting, nutrient management planning, soil carbon analysis, etc). The Scottish Government have also committed to shifting half of all agricultural support from unconditional to conditional by 2025 (I think this means increased conditionality given that all farmers already have to comply with cross-compliance or scheme conditions for any funding received). Although a conditionality testing programme was announced as part of the National Test Programme, I personally think it was a missed opportunity to get the industry also moving on improving biodiversity. The Farmer Led Groups suggested introducing biodiversity conditionality as a priority and I remain convinced that implementing a couple of new greening conditions from a suite of 20–30 simple biodiversity options could have been introduced to demonstrate to wider society that the industry and Scottish Government are committed and serious about delivering greater public value for public money.

The known-unknowns (the delivery model and framework): This is where it starts to get a little bit tricky for me. Whilst the Scottish Government's ambition is to remain aligned to the EU where possible, we are now operating outside the CAP (and its ongoing reform package) but within a yet to be confirmed UK Common Framework on agricultural support. This common framework essentially will replace the EU structures around agricultural support within the UK, and set the bounds of what delivery mechanisms are permissible to devolved administrations. Further, both the UK Internal Market Act and the Subsidy Control Bill may yet impact how agricultural support is delivered within the UK. These pieces of legislation could have long term implications on how we can structure support payments in Scotland, as there are inherent risks of accusations of 'competitive advantage' for any administration that maintains direct support whilst Defra are swiftly abandoning direct support in favour of environmental payments in England. Further, it is still unknown how we can best measure climate change emissions, biodiversity provisioning, water and air quality on farms in ways that can be used in a future conditional support scheme. Work needs to be done on measuring actions and/or outcomes that can enable the unique circumstances on individual farms and crofts to be accounted for in any future direct support scheme that rewards delivery of positive environmental outcomes. I remain adamant that we should not only support farmers to improve but rather incentivise attainment, meaning that all those delivering against defined outcomes get rewarded.

The unknown-unknowns (trade, WTO rules and science): Within agricultural policy there are a wide set of international rules established in the World Trade Organisation's Agreement on Agriculture. In light of climate change and biodiversity priorities it appears to me that there is now a need to revisit how countries are permitted to support agriculture – particularly where policy is focused on reducing emissions or improving the wider environment (it remains unknown if and how this could occur). The income forgone and additional cost model makes it challenging to provide income support for farmers that are delivering positive agri-environmental outcomes. Given that many Governments around the world appear to have an increased environmental focus in agricultural policy this likely needs serious consideration so there is a level playing field globally. This matters since non-compliance with WTO rules can lead to disputes, retaliatory actions, and long-term trade implications. Other unknown-unknowns include how climate change will impact on the farming calendar over the next 30-50 years, or indeed what agri-tech solutions will come forward to help mitigate and adapt to climate change. I'm a firm believer that scientific and agri-tech solutions will abound in the next decade as investment funds that have been tied up in oil and gas look for new green investment opportunities (remembering that the global population is also expected to grow to 11 billion by 2100). You only need to look at the rapid investment in methane inhibitors for livestock to see that science can help unlock more sustainable food production.

Donald Rumsfeld came in for a lot of criticism over his statement at the time, yet when you think about it, his statement fits with our experiences of both Brexit and Covid. We now live in a period of agricultural policy flux – where the bounds of agricultural policy objectives as we know them are being stretched beyond the comfort zone for many farmers.